

ROLE OF CLUSTER IN INNOVATIVE MANAGEMENT OF THE CONSTRUCTION NETWORK

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B.K. Abdusamatov

PhD. associate professor of the "Construction Economics and Management" department, Samarkand State University of Architecture and Construction

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Abstract: Ушбу мақола қурилиш тармоғини самарали бошқаришда минтақа қурилишига кластер моделини жорий этиш асосида, қурилишни самарали бошқарув тизимидаги муаммоларни ечишга қаратилган

Keywords: кластер, қурилиш, кластерни ривожлантириш концепсияси, қурилиш мажмуаси, стратегия, рақобат, кучмас мулк, модернизация

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Abstract: Данная статья направлена на решение задач эффективной системы управления строительством на основе внедрения кластерной модели строительства региона в эффективное управление строительной отрасли.

Keywords: кластер, строительство, концепция развития кластера, строительный комплекс, стратегия, конкуренция, недвижимость, модернизация.

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Abstract: This article is aimed at solving the problems of an effective construction management system based on the introduction of a cluster model of the construction of the region in the effective management of the construction industry.

Keywords: cluster, construction, cluster development concept, building complex, strategy, competition, real estate, modernization

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Today, the construction network is distinguished by its ongoing activities, structural changes in the economy of the country, and the implementation of urgent tasks in various social spheres.

Our state is doing a lot of work to further develop the construction industry.

In 2018, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to fundamentally improve the state management system in the field of construction" was adopted on the further development of the construction industry in the republic [1].

In 2019, the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the wide introduction of information and communication technologies in the construction industry" was adopted [2].

In 2020, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the strategy of modernization, rapid and innovative development of

the construction network of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2021-2025" was adopted [3].

The decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the strategy of modernization, rapid and innovative development of the construction network of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2021 - 2025" was adopted [4].

The adopted Decree is mainly aimed at increasing the capacity of the construction network through the effective use of innovations, investments, labor and material resources in order to ensure the successful implementation of economic development programs.

In order to further develop the construction industry and the production complex of building materials in the republic, to ensure the construction of affordable housing for the population in the regions, to reduce the imbalance of demand and supply in the housing construction market, in 2022 the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Supporting housing construction and building materials industry - "On additional measures of support" was adopted [5].

"These numbers are easy to say. Hard work is behind each of them. Because the value of a person, honoring a person is the most important issue in our attention.

For this purpose, in the last six years, we have built nearly 300,000 houses in our country, or 10 times more than in previous years" [6].

The above decisions and decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan are important because they are aimed at the noble goals of improving the way of life of the population and the development of social infrastructure in general.

The foundation for further improvement of the construction network in our republic has been created, that is, the need to choose one of the ways based on knowledge and practice that has been economically effective in the world markets in developed countries, and to continue the construction processes based on this way remains one of the main tasks of today.

This way, in our opinion, is a further improvement of the cluster, which today is very much looking for its solution in the construction industry.

"In the modern concept of business entities, the traditional division of the economy into sectors or sectors has lost its importance, and communication systems between firms and organizations, the creation of strategic alliances, and the use of the cluster approach become a priority issue" [7].

Compared to traditional building complexes, the cluster is based as fully as possible on the market principles of the organization of production and service provision. A cluster is an effective mechanism of construction complex cooperation, because the initiators of such a union are the enterprises of the construction

complex, which feel the need to unite in various forms to create competitive advantages.

"Connections formed for the strategic management of enterprises play a decisive role in identifying directions for introducing innovations, increasing labor productivity, reducing production costs, and ultimately in the fight against competition. Clusters are very suitable for the nature of competition and the sources of achieving competitive advantages [8].

The organization of networks and inter-network clusters oriented to interregional and foreign markets forms the basis of increasing industrial competitiveness. In this regard, Porter's cluster model as a means of increasing the competitiveness of the economy of a region or a country is widely used today in the development of economic policy in the whole world [9].

"S.A. Mokhnachev and E. S. Mokhnacheva consider clustering to be a network form of integration of various enterprises and networks. A cluster is presented as a network of enterprises and organizations connected by geographical location and final product production" [10].

"According to the American economist P. Krugman, "clusters are specialized constitutes a structural element of the labor market, from their influence of workers both at the time of employment and the work that has the necessary skills become givers [11]

Therefore, in the cluster, the integration of science, education, and production will be deepened, another favorable conditions will be created for the rapid introduction of new innovative technologies into practice.

Because, in order to improve the cluster model in our Republic, it is important to achieve high efficiency of the construction network. In fact, Sa has already found his approval

Thus, the cluster forms an association of economically connected industries located at the same time, mutually supporting each other's common development and increasing competitiveness. Within the framework of a single chain of value creation, which connects technology creators, market institutions and consumers of the large enterprises leading the cluster - production and delivery of certain products and services located in a limited area, interacting with each other.

This union, in the process of mutual cooperation of its separate parts, while harmonizing their characteristics, acquires new characteristics that are clearly and comprehensively manifested, especially in clusters organized by economic activity subjects.

The role of large business in the process of creating clusters is to attract small enterprises to carry out production on the basis of organic cooperation in active business and information cooperation. This cluster promotes the development of all

its participants and provides them with a competitive advantage over other isolated enterprises that do not have such strong interconnections.

The cluster creates an environment that is interested in the development of innovations, because its scientific developments allow to produce a competitive product for a relatively long time, which brings maximum profit to the investment unit [12]. The social effect of clustering in the construction cluster is the housing of the population

It is manifested in the increase in the level of provision with the existence of a service element in the form of banks in the cluster, regulation by the legal state, the stability of the cluster system with the guaranteed conditions of handing over housing to the population.

Today, the role of business communities and public organizations in the issue of self-regulation of the construction industry in the region is increasing. This is because the main part of its subjects is private property and off-budget investments. Therefore, based on the logic of the existence and development of the market, the task of the state is to determine the system of rules and norms, that is, the institutions for the development of competition, private initiative, and the formation of investment markets. Public associations are called upon to regulate relations within each market, between the market and the state.

The normal development and operation of the construction complex depends, first of all, on the balance of investment demand, the material and technical development of this field, the existence and efficiency of competitive institutions, and finally, the efficiency of the state administration.

But this requires the use of new approaches and methods of solving the problems and tasks of changes in the structures and behavior of construction organizations. The idea of clustering the construction complex in the region proposed in this article can serve as one of the ways to solve the problems.

The transition of the construction network in the region to the innovative type of development characteristic of the current stage of the region's economy is considered a necessary factor determining the contribution of the region to sustainable economic growth. In order to create a cluster, one must strive for a certain goal, which is a special addition to it should consist of giving properties, as a result of which the construction cluster participants resources. technology knowledge must be guaranteed [13]

Depending on the conditions of choosing a building cluster as an object of clustering. First, the implementation of many large investment projects in the region requires the construction of new objects (including social objects) and production objects.

Secondly, providing housing to the population of the region within the framework of the national project "Affordable and affordable housing for the citizens of the Republic" minimizes the social component of investment risks and to a certain extent contributes to the growth of consumption and labor potential.

Thirdly, problems accumulated in the field of construction do not have a negative impact on the general socio-economic development of the region and its investment environment.

The construction cluster unites all blocks (organizations) of the construction complex, which are enterprises that produce construction materials, construction organizations, enterprises that provide the relevant equipment and construction technologies, personnel training, design organizations, architectural firms, and organizations that sell and lease real estate.

Construction clusters have a number of unique features compared to regional clusters in other areas. When creating a construction cluster, it is necessary to take into account the basic rules of the cluster concept, which include the following:

- construction and related enterprises that make up the cluster have the opportunity to share costs related to the use of the same resources;
- geographical proximity of enterprises transport
- communication costs allows to reduce the concentration of enterprises in the region to the spread of hidden knowledge gives merit, that is, the personal experience of the employees of the companies included in the cluster.

It is clear from the above considerations that the core of the construction complex is the core of the cluster model, which is the largest competitive economic entity (suppliers), producer (builders), the market - the chain of operating entities, and after the construction cluster is established, the construction complex is also an effective manager. i think

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